

[勘誤 Erratum]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20985657>

Erratum: A Preliminary Study on Amphibian-Feeding Behavior of Hematophagous Diptera (Psychodidae, Culicidae, and Corethrellidae) in Taiwan Based on Citizen Science Data

JH-YU YOU^{1,2,*}, YEN-MIN LIN³

¹ Department of Life Sciences, National Chung Hsing University, Taichung 40227, Taiwan

² Amphibian Specialist Group, Species Survival Commission, International Union for the Conservation of Nature, Rue Mauverney 28, Gland 1196, Switzerland

³ Department of Entomology, National Taiwan University, No. 1, Sec. 4, Roosevelt Rd., Da'an Dist., Taipei City 10617, Taiwan

* Corresponding author: jhyu2007@gmail.com

Erratum: You & Lin (2026) preliminarily summarized and analyzed photo records of the amphibian-feeding behavior of hematophagous Diptera of Taiwan through citizen science data. However, You & Lin (2026) wrongly stated that “This study provides the first record of Phlebotominae feeding on amphibian blood in Asia, as well as the first direct observational evidence worldwide of this feeding behavior.” This statement should be corrected to “This study provides the first record of Phlebotominae feeding on amphibian blood in Taiwan.” Several studies have reported the blood-feeding behavior of Phlebotominae (Psychodidae) on amphibians from China, India and South Africa (Howlett, 1909, 1913; Feng & Chung, 1940; Braack *et al.*, 1981). Additionally, all instances of the word “Dipteran” in You & Lin (2026) should be corrected to “dipteran.” We thank Yu-Feng Tsai (Institute of Environmental and Occupational Health Sciences, National Taiwan University, Taiwan), who informed us of these mistakes and assisted with the search for related literature.

References

- Braack, H. H., Davidson, I. H., Ledger, J. A. & Lewis, D. J. 1981. Records of Sandflies (Diptera: Psychodidae: Phlebotominae) feeding on Amphibia, with A new record from the Kruger National Park. *Koedoe* 24 (1): 187–188.
- Feng, L.-C. & Chung, H.-L. 1940. *Phlebotomus squamirostris* Newstead, transmitter of *Trypanosoma bocagei* França in the toad, *Bufo bufo gargarizans* (Cantor). *Chinese Medical Journal Supplements* 3: 198–211.
- Howlett, F. M. 1909. Indian Sand-Flies. *Transactions of the Bombay Medical Congress* 3: 239–242.
- Howlett, F. M. 1913. The Natural Host of *Phlebotomus minutus*. *Indian Journal of Medical Research* 1 (1): 34–38.
- You, J.-Y. & Lin, Y.-M. 2026. A Preliminary Study on Amphibian-Feeding Behavior of Hematophagous Diptera in Taiwan Based on Citizen Science Data. *Taiwanese Journal of Entomological Studies* 11 (2): 5–10. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19498867>

勘誤：從公民科學觀察揭示臺灣吸血性雙翅目（蛾蚋科，蚊科，蛙蠓科）吸食兩生類行為之初探

游智宇^{1,2,*}, 林彥旻³

¹ 國立中興大學 生命科學系 40227 臺灣臺中市南區興大路 145 號 生命科學大樓

² 國際自然保育聯盟 兩棲類專家小組 1196 瑞士格朗莫韋爾內街 28 號

³ 國立臺灣大學昆蟲學系 10617 臺北市大安區羅斯福路四段 1 號

* 通訊作者： jhyu2007@gmail.com

勘誤：You & Lin (2026) 透過公民科學研究，初步對臺灣吸血性雙翅目吸食兩生類的紀錄進行整理與分析。然而，You & Lin (2026) 在內文中錯誤地表示該篇為「亞洲第一筆蛾蚋科之白蛉亞科吸食兩生類血液的行為紀錄，同時也是全球首筆蛾蚋科吸食兩生類的影像紀錄」。事實上過去已有多篇文獻記錄到亞洲和非洲的白蛉亞科 (Phlebotominae) 物種吸食兩生類動物血液的行為 (Howlett, 1909, 1913; Feng & Chung, 1940; Braack *et al.*, 1981)，因此這句陳述應該修改為「臺灣第一筆蛾蚋科之白蛉亞科吸食兩生類血液的行為紀錄」。此外，內文中所有的「Dipteran」為拼寫錯誤，皆應修正為「dipteran」。我們感謝蔡育峰 (臺灣大學環境與職業健康科學研究所) 注意到內文的錯誤並協助提供相關文獻。

稿件收到 Received: 14 April 2026

稿件接受 Accepted: 23 April 2026

稿件出版 Published: 25 September 2026